

Using ICT in Education of Special Needs Children

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Abstract:

Digital technologies have become a regular part of lives of special needs children. They can primarily come across them in their families, but they can also play an important role in education. To integrate a computer successfully into special needs education requires suitable engagement of pedagogues who are computer literate and who then become familiar with suitable educational programs and change their existing methods of work. Millions of students across the country cannot benefit fully from a traditional educational program because they have a disability that impairs their ability to participate in a typical classroom environment. For these students, computer-based technologies can play an especially important role. Not only can computer technology facilitate a broader range of educational activities to meet a variety of needs for students with mild learning disorders, but adaptive technology now exists that can enable even those students with severe disabilities to become active learners in the classroom alongside their peers who do not have disabilities. The article concludes that there exists a considerable potential in the educational uses of ICTs alongside with many challenges and dangers. Useful recommendations were made to maximize the benefits of ICT in special needs education.

Introduction:

Special education is the practice of educating students with special educational needs in a way that addresses their individual differences and needs. Ideally, this process involves the individually planned and systematically monitored arrangement of teaching procedures, adapted equipment and materials, and accessible settings. These interventions are designed to help individuals with special needs achieve a higher level of personal self-sufficiency and success in school and in their community, that may not be available if the student were only given access to a typical classroom education.

Common special needs include learning disabilities (such as dyslexia), communication disorders, emotional and behavioral disorders (such as ADHD and ADD), physical disabilities (such as Brittle Bone Disease, Cerebral Palsy, Muscular Dystrophy, Spinal Bifida, and Frederich's Ataxia), and developmental disabilities (such as autism spectrum disorders and intellectual disability). Students with these kinds of special needs are likely to benefit from additional educational services such as different approaches to teaching, the use of technology, a specifically adapted teaching area, or a resource room. Special education is designed specifically for students with special needs.

Use of Technology for the Education of Special Child:

Special education in developed countries is often regarded as a service rather than a place. Integration can reduce social stigmas and improve academic achievement for many students. Technology in the classroom can serve as a great

equalizer. When used correctly, technology can help teachers differentiate instruction and empower students with special needs. There are different devices and apps for students with all types of special needs.

Help and ICT for struggling students:

One of the most common problems teachers face with students with special needs is being able to include them in classroom activities. For students who have a learning disability, simply being included can be an empowering experience. However, when a student has a deficit in basic reading or math skills, it can be hard for them to participate successfully in the same activities other students are doing.

Technology allows teachers to easily differentiate. There are tons of programs available that let teachers adjust the difficulty level of reading assignments, for example. With technology, teachers can make small changes to assignments, such as adding additional help or resources, without providing a ton of extra materials for just a few students. When it's impossible for every student to do the same activity, it's easier for students to work on different activities using technology. If every student has an iPad in their hands, other students won't notice when a few classmates are working on something different. This can make it less embarrassing for students who need remediation.

Teach Life Skills to Special Needs Child:

Special needs world, the most basic skills are called Adaptive Living Skills, or ADL's. More advanced skills, such as doing laundry, catching a bus, or following a daily schedule, are sometimes called Life Skills or Skills of Daily Living. While

these skills aren't critical for survival, they are extremely important for anyone who plans to work and recreate in a modern community.

Everyone needs certain skills to simply get through the day. Skills related to eating, dressing, and personal hygiene are absolute requirements for anyone wishing to live even a semi-independent life. In addition to these very basic skills are the many skills we use each day to navigate life at home and in the community.

Most people learn ADLs and many of the skills of daily living at a young age. They learn through a combination of instruction, imitation, and trial and error. For example, a child may learn to bathe himself by remembering the experience of being bathed, by imitating a parent's actions, and by discovering for herself that if you run very hot water for too long the water will be too hot for comfort.

How Life Skills Are Taught to Children With Special Needs:

Teachers, therapists, and parents have developed a set of techniques that, together or separately, can be very effective in teaching life skills to children with special needs. And the good news is that these techniques can be equally effective for teaching just about any skill to just about anyone—no matter what their abilities or challenges.

Step One: Task Analysis. Task analysis is a process for breaking down any given task into its component parts. For example, brushing teeth includes finding a toothbrush, toothpaste, and cup, putting toothpaste on the brush, brushing the bottom teeth, rinsing, brushing the top teeth, rinsing again, cleaning the brush, and putting all the equipment away properly.

Step Two: Creating a Visual Guide. Many parents create visual guides to help their children with special needs to make sense of, remember, and get comfortable with the steps involved in a task. The visual guide can include photos or clip-art style images of each step in the process.

Step Three: Prompting and Fading. At first, a child with special needs may need a lot of help in remembering and properly completing each step in a task. Prompting may involve physical, hand-over-hand help. As they learn, parents will start to "fade" the prompts. First they'll stop using hand-over-hand help, and instead provide only verbal prompts ("don't forget to rinse the toothbrush!").

Then they'll start to fade even the verbal prompts. When no prompts are required, the child has learned the task!

Facts: Technology can be the great equalizer in a classroom with diverse learners. Whereas teachers can find it difficult to differentiate instruction for 30+ students in one class, all with different needs and abilities, "assistive technology" (devices and

software to assist students with disabilities) can often help teachers personalize lessons and skills enhancement to each child. Children with learning disabilities often have better technology skills than their teachers and are drawn to computers and other gadgets, so using them in the classroom makes perfect sense. For children with physical disabilities, technology can give access to learning opportunities previously closed to them. E-readers help students turn book pages without applying dexterity, and voice adaptive software can help students answer questions without needing to write. Computers are engaging and more advanced than the typical modified lesson allows. The widely-used teacher education textbook *Educating Exceptional Children* has a special section in each chapter focused on assistive technology explaining how it is used with exceptionalities ranging from giftedness to autism.

Assistive technology is not always just for students with disabilities; it can be used to help any student with motivation, academic skills, and social development. Here are some helpful resources for teachers looking for assistive technology for their students:

1. **UNC's Center for Literacy and Disability Studies** uses technology in their mission to promote literacy and communication for individuals of all ages with disabilities. The Center has developed a three-part video on reading assessment and assistive technology that explains evidence-based practices of improving literacy through technology. Additionally, the Center has developed "alternative pencils" for students with disabilities who cannot hold a traditional pencil or see a page, including children with deaf-blindness. These technologies include alphabet eye gaze frames allowing children to "point" to letters with their eyes, onscreen keyboards that are controlled by switches, and electronic flipcharts.
2. **LEARN NC** offers an extensive set of resources to help teachers meet the needs of all learners, including "Reaching Every Learner: Differentiating Instruction in Theory and Practice," a series of articles and web conferences about differentiation. In addition, LEARN NC's technology integration page provides links to web resources, lesson plans, articles, and online courses designed to help educators incorporate technology into their teaching
3. **Voice Thread** is a free software program that captures student voices and photos in order to collaborate on a topic. It is a technological substitute for written papers and allows students freedom to narrate their own projects.

4. **Sounding Board** is an iPad/iPod Touch app that lets a student turn their device into a story board communicator. Students with writing disabilities and communication disorders can use the symbols to create their own messages in the same way that traditional symbol boards work, but easily and with a limitless supply of symbols.
5. **TechMatrix** offers consumer guides and links to software and assistive technology devices for students with disabilities. The site is sponsored by the National Center for Technology Innovation and the Center for Implementing Technology in Education. TechMatrix gives information and links to resources for teaching science, math, reading, and writing using technology with special education students.

Ways to Use Technology in the Special Education Classroom:

Technology and special education classrooms:

In developing new technology, software and hardware companies have not overlooked the spectrum of special needs and special education students. Technology in special education classrooms is an industry within an industry and it is constantly developing and improving products for special needs.

1. Operating Systems:

Just about every operating system available has something for people with special needs. Both Microsoft and Apple, the creators of the two most prevalent operating systems, Windows 7 and OS X, offer a number of enhancements that enable users of different impairments to use the system. Microsoft's 'Ease of Access' center in the Windows operating system, as well as Apple's OS X, offer options that allow for using the computer without a monitor for the blind, adding visual prompts and eliminating sounds for the deaf, and alternate input devices for those with mobility deficiencies. These options are available in the base design of each system and do not cost users anything extra.

2. Braille displays:

There is no limit to what technology in special education classrooms can accomplish. Braille displays offer the ability read text that is sent to the machine by activating pins on a multi-cell display. They are available cheaply for reading text line by line while more expensive versions can read text, allow for text input and SMS texting, and help with navigation around the computer. They work with a cable and also come in a Bluetooth wireless version. Some Braille displays are even able to operate with smart phones and PDA's.

3. Word prediction software:

Word prediction software simply predicts the words that are being typed to reduce the number of keystrokes used to input the word. Once several

letters of the word are typed, a list of words pops up and the student selects the correct word. Some versions of the software base the list of words on the letters keyed and other versions will base the choice on context and grammar.

4. Tablets and I Pads:

Tablets and I Pads are the hottest must haves in the technology market. These devices can be used like a computer, an imaging device, a camera, a projector, a mouse, a keyboard, and a remote device for a white boards. The use of tablets and I Pads as technology in special education classrooms is limitless and app developers, parents, specialists and doctors are always searching for more unique ways to employ these devices.

5. Apps :

Apple's App Store and Google's Android App Market both offer a number of apps designed to assist in the use of technology in special education classrooms. Though sometimes they may be a little difficult to locate, Eric Sailors, a speech-language pathologist who has developed several apps for special needs children, has compiled a list of apps available in Apple's App Store and provides a short description of each. This list will assist teachers in finding useful apps quickly so they may work with their children more effectively. Alternately, the website Bridging Apps has developed a community of people directly concerned with the education of those with special needs and helps people to develop and share ideas about programs, apps and the use of technology in special education classrooms.

Conclusion:

Most students with disabilities can and do benefit from technology in the classroom. Incorporating technology increases students' motivation to learn and personalizes lessons to a student's individual needs. Even the students with the most severe and profound disabilities can use assistive technology to join a classroom of typical students, and their potential can be reached in ways we didn't have before. The use of technology in special education classrooms is still in its infancy. As developers see new markets for their technology and educators and specialists create new ideas that develop into hardware and software, the choices will grow. But, there are currently many options to choose from and a simple search can produce a number of ideas that can be employed in the classroom right away, with little investment.

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